

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Studies on Property Enhancement by Graphene Oxide in Polymer-based Composites serviced at Low Temperature Environment

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Introduction

Advanced Composites at Low Temperature Environment

Applications servicing at low temperature

Aerospace & Aircraft industries

Rocket

Aircraft

Fuel tank

Space station

Cryogenic equipment

LN₂ tank for vehicles

Cryotherapy chamber

Thermonuclear
Experimental Reactor

Liquid gas tank storage

Aircraft industries

Composite structures

Lightweight

Easy to manufacture

One-piece components

(No. of screws & rivets ↓)

Aircraft using 50% CFRP* by weight in airframe structure, compared with conventional aircraft using 3% CFRP

Approximately **20% lighter**

Life-cycle CO₂ emissions:

Conventional aircraft
395,000t -CO₂ emissions

Aircraft of 50% CFRP
368,000t -CO₂ emissions

= **27,000** t-CO₂ reduction per aircraft/decade

Source: The Japan Carbon Fiber Manufacturers Association

Left: Composite Structure
Right: Aluminium Structure

Low temperature issue

At low temperature, differential coefficients of thermal expansion (CTEs) between matrix and fibre may lead to debond between them, and cause structural fracture

Problems:

- Brittleness of polymer
- High thermal stress
- Low energy absorption (low impact resistance)
- Crack initiation and propagation (catastrophic failure may occur)

Cracking

Height (feet)	Temp (°F)	Temp (°C)
5,000	41.17	5
10,000	23.36	-5
15,000	5.55	-15
20,000	-12.26	-24.5
25,000	-30.05	-34.5
30,000	-47.83	-44.3
35,000	-65.61	-54.2
40,000	-69.70	-56.7
60,000	-69.70	-56.7
100,000	-51.10	-46.1
150,000	19.40	-7

Delamination

Interlaminated Shear Crack

Graphene oxide

Characteristics of Graphene Oxide (GO)

- Unique two dimensional structure
- Oxygen-containing functional groups
- Dissolve in organic or inorganic solvents
- Large specific surface area

Production of Graphene Oxide (GO)

- Modified Hummer's method
- Oxidation + Exfoliation

Electrophoretic deposition (EPD)

- GO is negatively-charged
- Fabric is connected to positive sign
- GO moves toward fabric and attaches on it

GO/CFRP composites at Low temperature

- GO-containing CFRP composites exhibit greater properties
- Oxygen-containing functional groups
- Large specific surface area
- Greater mechanical interlocking
- Improvement is more obvious at LT
- Unique thermal behaviour of GO (CTE: -7 to $-0.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$)

As-received fabric
Plain & clean surface

De-sized fabric
Well-defined striation

GO-coated fabric
Wrinkled structure

Sample/Properties	Room Temperature		Low Temperature	
	Flexural strength (MPa)	Percentage improvement (%)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Percentage improvement (%)
Pristine	443.91	0	408.24	0
GO-EP/CWF	523.67	17.97	508.09	24.46
GO-CWF/EP	609.54	37.31	602.66	47.62

Sample/Properties	Room Temperature		Low Temperature	
	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Percentage improvement (%)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Percentage improvement (%)
Pristine	51.73	0	46.23	0
GO-EP/CWF	54.40	5.16	52.16	12.82
GO-CWF/EP	58.21	12.53	57.00	23.30

GO/CFRP composites at Low temperature

• Dispersing GO into epoxy (GO-EP)

- Less matrix adhered on the fiber
- Surface of some fiber is neat

• *Enhancements are due to*

- ❖ *Effective bonding between GO and epoxy*
- ❖ *Suppression of crack propagation in epoxy*

• Coating GO onto fabric (GO-CWF)

- More matrix adhered on the fiber

• *Enhancements are due to*

- ❖ *Surface polarity, wettability and roughness of CWF*
- ❖ *Greater mechanical interlocking between CWF and epoxy via GO*

Schematic diagrams of failure at interface of (a) pristine, (b) GO-EP/CWF and (c) GO-CWF/EP composites.

SEM morphologies of the fracture surface of (a) pristine, (b) GO-EP/CWF and (c) GO-CWF/EP composites at LT

Hung et al. Composite Part A (120) pp56-63, May 2019

GO/CFRP composites at Low temperature

- Thermal expansion of GO compensates the shrinkage of epoxy at low temperature
- Retain the enhanced strength by GO

Debonding

Sample/ Properties	Room Temperature		Low Temperature	
	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)
Pristine	443.91	51.73	408.24	46.23
GO/CFRP	609.54	58.21	602.66	57.00

GO/CFRP composites at Low temperature

GO/CFRP composites exhibit greater E' than pristine composites, indicating that greater stiffness of composite is resulted with the presence of GO, which enhances the chemical bonding and mechanical interlocking between fibre and matrix to form a stiff and strong composite.

GO restricts the mobility of epoxy molecular chains and serves as an extra reinforcement to stiffen the composites. The composites at LT shows a similar trend with greater E' than those at RT due to the cryogenic toughening of the epoxy matrix.

DMA curves of pristine, GO-EP/CWF and GO-CWF/EP composites treated at RT and LT